

Optimizing Throughput and Energy with Intent-Based 6G Network Slicing: Conflict Handling

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Abstract—The advent of Sixth-Generation (6G) mobile networks is expected to facilitate new services, each with diverse Quality of Service (QoS) intent requirements. Digital Service Providers (DSPs) must align with these requirements by prioritizing critical intents and reconfiguring resources when necessary. Network Slicing (NS) and Intent-Based Network (IBN) management have become essential tools for addressing the intent expectations of both current and future 6G services. This paper presents a robust optimization framework aimed at maximizing throughput while minimizing Energy Consumption (EC). The framework creates isolated network slices tailored to specific QoS intents, ensuring compliance with the performance metrics defined in Service Level Agreements (SLAs). Our findings indicate that, while this approach effectively meets SLA targets for specific slices, it conflicts with intent expectation of other slices and can compromise their performance, leading to significant degradation in throughput and EC costs. For instance, enforcing SLA objective for one specific slice means improving slice capacity while it has a huge decrease in the average throughput up to 65% and a decreased EC cost up to 81%.

Index Terms—6G, Intent-Based Network Management, Network Slicing, QoS, SLA, Intent Conflict Handling

I. INTRODUCTION

The upcoming Sixth Generation (6G) mobile communications promise revolutionary improvements, enabling new services with diverse Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. The envisioned 6G expansion builds upon ITU-2020 [1] main services—enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), and ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (uRLLC)—and enables new services introduced by ITU-2030 [2]—Immersive Communication (IC), Hyper Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (HRLLC), Massive Communication (MC), Ubiquitous Connectivity (UC), Artificial Intelligence and Communication (AIC), and Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISC)—each aiming for different QoS intents, which should be addressed by Digital Service Providers (DSPs).

Challenges. The adoption of virtualization in Radio Access Network (RAN) architecture, facilitated by standardization bodies like O-RAN [3] and NG-RAN [4] unveils new network configuration and management challenges for practical 6G RAN deployments to serve services with varied QoS intents. The DSPs need to decide the optimal distribution of functions among RAN elements, referred to as *Functional Split (FS)*, which presents significant challenges [5], [6]. Each FS imposes different capacity requirements in Transport Network (TN) and utilizes different computing resources. This complicates the design of TN network further due to the virtualization

which allows for having multiple FS choices per RAN element. Moreover, in 6G, DSPs must evaluate service intent expectations and targets while handling numerous and possibly conflicting End-to-End (E2E) intents including—throughput, connection density, reliability, and energy—, which is complex. The main challenge is resolving intent conflicts when different services within the same intent or across different intents have conflicting targets. For instance, addressing a throughput target $target_1 =: throughput > threshold_1$ for IC service may conflict with energy target $target_2 =: energy > threshold_2$ of MC service and degrade its performance.

Potential Solutions. Network Slicing (NS) enabled with—Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV)—is one of the main technologies providing on-demand virtual NSs tailored to different verticals and service requirements [5], [7]. Various service types, such as IC, HRLLC, and MC, have unique NS requirements that can be classified into different Network Slice Subnets (NSSs) consisting of RAN, TN, and Core Network (CN), as defined in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [8]. Another key technology, Intent-Based Network (IBN), abstracts application layer from the underlying infrastructure, and automates NS by translating high-level User Equipment (UE) intents into detailed network configurations, aligning network design, deployment, and management with business objectives and diverse vertical intents [9]. The primary function of IBN is intent translation, which entails identifying items within UE intents and translating them into corresponding network configurations and resource requirements [10]. Different studies focus on IBN management, however, they often fail to handle QoS intent requirements by identifying slice intent conflicts and mitigating identified conflicts when both energy and throughput metrics are optimized. Hence, this study fills this gap by proposing a multi-objective optimization framework that maximizes throughput and minimizes EC costs by fulfilling the intent requests while adhering to network resource constraints. We formulate a robust optimization framework, which creates isolated slices with customized FSs based on the distinctive QoS intents, assuring that each slice is tailored to fulfill specific performance metrics outlined in corresponding Service Level Agreement (SLA) objectives. Our framework detects intent conflicts and handles them by adjusting SLA thresholds to fully serve the slices with higher priorities.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II studies the state of the art for NS and IBN management. Section III describes the system model and problem statement. Section IV, presents our robust optimization framework as a novel proposal to jointly optimize throughput and Energy Consumption (EC) cost for the life-cycle of intents. Section V provides a performance evaluation of our framework. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Several relevant works have studied FS optimization. More specifically, [11] formulates a joint routing and FS optimization to maximize centralization degree of the network. Authors in [12] jointly optimize FS and locations of RAN elements, their resources, and the routing for data flow while minimizing network operation cost. However, despite their insightful conclusions, the concepts of NS and IBN to address service requirements are neglected in both of these works. In this context, our recent works in [5], [6] present a joint routing and FS optimization while considering RAN NS. However, prior studies lack E2E NS and considering IBN concept to evaluate intent conflict detection and resolution. Another shortage of these works is that the EC metric is neglected. There are some studies focusing on IBN and 6G application scenarios with effective management of conflicting intents [2], [13]. For example, authors in [14] propose an IBN platform for efficient management and orchestration of 5G NS using deep learning. Another study in [15] explores conflict resolution solutions in IBN for effective network management, focusing on RAN domain. In spite of these contributions, yet, significant challenges persist in the management of IBN, where current studies often have limitations in (i) accommodating customized slice intents with diverse QoS requirements, (ii) assuring each slice has adequate access to network resources to fulfill its intents, and (iii) effectively re-configuring slice configurations and prioritizing critical slice intents in resource-constrained scenarios. To address these gaps, our proposal, which maximizes the throughput and minimizes EC cost, aims to handle the complexities of QoS intents by creating tailored slices with customized FSs and handling intent conflicts.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model contains a network model incorporating RAN elements, CN, and a TN connecting them. Finally, the traffic demand details UEs' traffic with different QoS intents.

A. Network Model

We consider E2E network architecture composed of RAN, CN, and TN connecting CN and RAN elements through an integrated packet-based Crosshaul (CH) network [16]. The RAN is composed of fully virtualized components including a Central Unit (vCU), Distributed Units (vDUs), and Radio Units (vRUs). The accommodation of network functions among RAN elements depends exclusively on the adopted FS, where RAN deployers and DSPs aim to support two different FSs as specified in [17]. Hence, we consider two FSs as Integrated FSs (IFSs) among RAN elements; one FS as the Low Layer Split (LLS) between the vDU and vRU, and another FS as the

High Layer Split (HLS) between the vCU and vDU. Fig. 1 illustrates the scheme of different IFSs that are represented on top of the system model.

Fig. 1: Scheme of two different IFSs over the system model.

Our network architecture considers CH network design and focuses on a fully connected network topology, represented as a graph $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{L})$, where, \mathcal{V} defines a set of CN depicted as node-0, n_0 , a vCU node-1 n_1 , vDU node-2 n_2 . The \mathcal{A} corresponds to a set of vRUs, and \mathcal{L} indicates a set of links that connect these elements. In this case, $\mathcal{M} = \{V + A\}$ refers to the complete set of nodes, where $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{A}$. We also define a set $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{M} \setminus \{n_0\}$, which includes all nodes except n_0 . The set of links, \mathcal{L} , is defined as $\mathcal{L} = \{l_{i,j} : i, j \in \mathcal{M}\}$. Each link $l_{i,j} \in \mathcal{L}$ possesses a capacity of $\omega_{i,j} \geq 0$ (in b/s). Note that vDU (*i.e.*, n_2) itself is responsible for processing traffic of vRUs using a pool of Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs) in a Virtual Machine (VM), similarly, vCU (*i.e.*, n_1) processes traffic of vDUs.

B. Traffic Demand

For demand, we use a set \mathcal{U} of U UEs, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{U} = \{1, \dots, U\}$ and service type $s \in \mathcal{S}$, where $\mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, s\}$ with different QoS intents, where the UEs' intent is characterized by their specific intent profile the λ_u^s that defines the required data rate of UE u with service type s . We assume that the transmitted power per Physical Resource Blocks (PRB) is equal, where ρ^a defines the number of PRBs per vRU a , and we will use a path-loss model that depends on distance [18].

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

We propose a novel optimization framework that formulates the intent life-cycle of UEs that involves three main modules namely *intent interface*, *intent fulfillment*, and *intent assurance*. The first module interprets UEs' information and profiles UEs' intents, then the second module translates intents and creates customized slice intents tailored to meet the specific needs of intents. Finally, the intent assurance module verifies SLA objectives' validity for each slice's intent. We further discuss the specific intents modular and their corresponding translated constraints, which are then combined to create an E2E optimization model for intent-driven NS management.

A. Intent Interface

This module classifies the received UEs based on their intent information and profiles UE intents. Accordingly, we first define service type $s \in \mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, s\}$ based on the profile of received UEs and associate their intents. Where

$s = 1$ implies HRLLC service, $s = 2$ represents MC service, and finally $s = 3$ indicates IC service, respectively, and we consider throughput, EC, and connection density as the intent expectation of UEs. Within this concept, the tiling scheme, also referred to as mixed numerology [19], serves as a fundamental radio feature that facilitates NS at RAN level. This approach allows for the customization of network resources and using different Sub Carrier Spacing (SCS). This offers the adaptability needed to cater to diverse service requirements through flexible SCSs to align with the specific intents of various services. Each tile comprises time-frequency resources that share the same numerology, allowing UEs to be assigned to specific tiles (per slice). Besides, UE can use only a single numerology at a given time slot due to physical layer constraints [20]. We thus consider a tailored numerology for each slice based on their intent requirements [21]. For HRLLC slice, a larger SCS to meet latency requirements, is useful. The MC may use a lower bandwidth to save device energy and increase coverage. Finally, IC slice uses a shorter SCS to minimize control overhead. Accordingly, the SCS of each type of numerology is varied as $\mu_s \in \{15\text{KHz}, 30\text{KHz}, 60\text{KHz}\}$. Accordingly, for IC slice $\mu_1 = 15$, MC slice $\mu_2 = 30$, and finally HRLLC slice $\mu_3 = 60$.

B. Intent Fulfillment

This module manages processing intents from UEs' arrival to serving them in the network. It mainly involves the intent translation process into network resource requirements—including the spectrum, CH capacity, EC, and CPU VNF costs required by a UE—and the slice intent creation process. We thus create a slice intent template derived from the pre-calculated network resource requirements associated with certain UE intents, we then allocate the corresponding resources for each UE intent. We assume that each slice s has a set of UEs presenting similar traffic patterns with identical intents, and each UE is connected to vRU a , defined as:

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} I_u^{a,s} \leq 1, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (1)$$

The binary variable $I_u^{a,s} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether UE is associated to vRU a . We next calculate the spectrum usage required by UEs and translate it for each slice in terms of PRB, which has 12 sub-carriers, thus the bandwidth of a PRB per slice s can be defined as $v_s = 12 \cdot \mu_s$. Let's define $\rho^{a,s}$ as a variable to be the number of PRBs dynamically allocated to the s -th slice at vRU a , as:

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} v_s \cdot \rho^{a,s} \leq \varpi, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \quad (2)$$

where ϖ is the total bandwidth. Furthermore, we define the transmission rate per PRB using Shannon's theory:

$$\eta_u^{a,s} = v_s \cdot \log_2(1 + \delta_u^{a,s}), \quad (3)$$

where $\delta_u^{a,s}$ refers to the SNR between UE u of service type s and vRU a . Next, we compute the desired PRB for UE u using $\rho_u^{a,s} = \lceil \frac{\lambda_u^s}{\eta_u^{a,s}} \rceil$ and instantiate a slice for each service s . Hence, the overall PRB needed by all connected UEs from different

slices should not surpass the total available PRB in the vRU a :

$$\rho^a \geq \sum_{(s,u) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} I_u^{a,s} \cdot \rho_u^{a,s}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (4)$$

Functional Split Selection. The association of each IFS, defined in Section III, could be used for different NSs according to the slice intent requirements. For example, for HRLLC service ($s = 1$), it creates the HRLLC slice template that traverses from CN to vCU, and within RAN uses IFS 2, capitalizing HLS 2 between vCU and vDU, and LLS 6 between vDU and vRU. Conversely, for the IC services, it utilizes IFS 4 to create IC slice template where it capitalizes HLS 4 between vCU and vDU, and LLS 7 between vDU and vRU elements emphasizing the framework's adaptability to diverse service requirements. We thus define the variable $f_n^s \in \{0, 1\}$ for $n \in \mathcal{N}$ where $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, 4\}$ to adjust the HLS among vCU-vDU and among LLS vDU-vRUs. Accordingly, if IFS 1 is adapted for slice s , then $f_1^{a,s} = 1$, defining HLS option 2 between vCU-vDU and LLS option 7 between vDU-vRU. If IFS 2 is selected, then $f_2^{a,s} = 1$, representing HLS option 2 between vCU-vDU and LLS option 6 between vDU-vRU. Likewise, a similar pattern can be realized from Table I for IFS 3 and IFS 4.

$$f_n^s = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if slice } s \text{ uses IFS } n \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

The FS association should respect the following constraint where each slice cannot use more than one FS, as:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\mathcal{N}} f_n^s = 1 \quad \text{for } s \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad (6)$$

TABLE I: Functions' allocation and CH requirements for traffic λ_u^s with 400 MHz bandwidth; Downlink: MCS 256 QAM, 64 antenna ports and 8 MIMO layers [22].

IFS	[HLS,LLS]	CH Load (Gbps)	CPU Load (%) [CU,DU,RU]
1	[2, 7]	$[\lambda_u^s, 50.4]$	[20, 63, 17]
2	[2, 6]	$[\lambda_u^s, 1.02\lambda_u^s + 1.5]$	[20, 15, 65]
3	[4, 6]	$[\lambda_u^s, 1.02\lambda_u^s + 1.5]$	[21, 14, 65]
4	[4, 7]	$[\lambda_u^s, 50.4]$	[21, 52, 17]

VNFs Computation Requirements. The CPU computation cost pertaining to VNFs deployment is another UE intent requirement, referred to as VNF cost (CPU load in Table I) that needs to be translated into network resource requirements. As such, the VNFs costs are explored, where for vRU a is defined by:

$$\sum_{(s,u,n) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot v_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s \leq \kappa_a, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (7)$$

where $v_n^{a,s}$ is CPU computational load of VNFs (in %) belonging to slice s at vRU a when $f_n^s = 1$. For instance, once IFS 1 ($f_1^s = 1$) is selected $v_1^{a,s}$ (b/s) is the CPU computational load required to process the VNFs at vRU a , which is 17%. Similarly, $v_2^{a,s}$ is set for IFS 2 ($f_2^s = 1$), $v_3^{a,s}$ for IFS 3 ($f_3^s = 1$), and $v_4^{a,s}$ for IFS 4 ($f_4^s = 1$). It affirms that CPU computation capacity requested for the processing of all VNFs

inside vRU shall be lower than CPU computation capacity available in vRU a (κ_a).

For vDU:

$$\sum_{(a,s,u,n) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot \tilde{v}_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s \leq \kappa_{n_2} \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{v}_n^{a,s}$ is CPU computational load of VNFs at vDU, set by using Table I. For vCU it can be defined as:

$$\sum_{(a,s,u,n) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot \tilde{v}_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s \leq \kappa_{n_1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{v}_n^{a,s}$ is CPU computational cost of VNFs at vCU.

Energy Consumption Requirements. The EC, which includes CPU power, cooling, and UE traffic load-related consumption, is another UE intent need that needs to be translated into network resource requirements associated with VNFs deployment [23]. Accordingly, the EC of these VNFs for both parts (RAN and CN) is examined, as for vRU a is defined by:

$$E_a = \sum_{(s,u,n) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} \frac{(I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot v_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s)}{\kappa_a} \cdot \epsilon^{a,s}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (10)$$

where $\epsilon^{a,s}$ is the energy coefficient of the traffic load (KWh) belonging to slice s at vRU a when $f_n^s = 1$. It ensures energy power requested for the traffic load of slice s shall be lower than the energy power capacity available in vRU a (E_a).

For vDU:

$$E_{n_2} = \sum_{(a,s,u,n) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} \frac{(I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot \tilde{v}_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s)}{\kappa_{n_2}} \cdot \epsilon^{n_2,s}, \quad (11)$$

Similarly, for vCU it can be set as:

$$E_{n_1} = \sum_{(a,s,u,n) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{N}} \frac{(I_u^{a,s} \cdot \lambda_u^s \cdot \tilde{v}_n^{a,s} \cdot f_n^s)}{\kappa_{n_1}} \cdot \epsilon^{n_1,s}, \quad (12)$$

Accordingly, we consider the cost to install VMs and run VNFs along with the cost of EC expressed in monetary units, which, gives the total EC cost for VMs for each slice, as:

$$E_{tot} = \sum_{w \in \mathcal{W}} (E_w \cdot \beta_w) \cdot C_s \quad (13)$$

where β_w is the corresponding cost to install VMs in each network component, and C_s is the cost of EC (\$).

CH Network Requirements. This requirement is related to CH network requirement that delivers traffic towards UEs over path $p \in \mathcal{P}^r$ traversing from CN to vRU a . All potential paths between vRU a and CN are represented by \mathcal{P}^a . Hence, traffic supported by vRU a through path p represented as t_p^a :

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^a} t_p^a = \sum_{(s,u) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} \lambda_u^s \cdot I_u^{a,s} \cdot T_u^{a,s} \quad (14)$$

where $T_u^{a,s}$ is the CH load due to the traffic injected by UE u , which relies on the selected IFS from Table I. For instance, when slice s uses IFS 2, we have the CH load of λ_u^s for HLS (vCU-vDU) plus $1.02 \cdot \lambda_u^s + 1.5$ for LLS (vDU-vRU). Accordingly, link capacity $\omega_{i,j}$ (b/s) should respect:

$$\sum_{(a,s,p) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{P}^a} t_p^a \cdot J_{i,j}^p \leq \omega_{i,j}, \forall j \neq i \in \mathcal{M}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (15)$$

The variable $J_{i,j}^p \in \{0, 1\}$ implies whether path p includes link $l_{i,j}$.

C. Slice Intent Assurance

In this module, slice intent assurance verifies SLA objectives' validity for each slice's intent. Different SLA thresholds can be imposed for the considered intents such as—connection density, throughput, and EC cost—to assess the performance of each network slice. The assessed SLAs in this work focus on maintaining the percentage of UEs under control. Therefore, ensuring the SLA is linked to each service accepted by the network. Hence, we examine connection density, referred to as slice capacity in 3GPP [24], and set it as a minimum threshold for each slice, serving as the intent expectation target. It represents the maximum number of UEs that can be accommodated within that slice, as:

$$\sum_{(a,u) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{U}} I_u^{a,s} \geq \tau^s \cdot \vartheta^s, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (16)$$

where ϑ^s is the total number of UEs with service type s . Thus, the minimum number of UEs that should meet the required QoS is $\tau^s \cdot \vartheta^s$. The last two intents are considered as common intents of all services, and we thus take them as the main objective function as follows.

Objective. The main goal of DSP is maximizing the satisfaction of UE intents which is connected to achieved throughput while minimizing EC of the network for creating NSs, which can be defined as:

$$\max_{I,t,\rho} O(\cdot) + \min_{I,t,\rho} E_{tot}(\cdot) \quad (17)$$

where $O = \sum_{(a,s,u) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} \lambda_u^s \cdot I_u^{a,s}$ is the first objective to maximize throughput and E_{tot} is the second objective to minimize EC. Putting the overall objective along with all the above constraints together, we introduce mathematical problem \mathbb{P} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}: \min_{I,t,\rho} & E(I, t, \rho) - O(I, t, \rho) \\ \text{s.t:} & \\ & (1)-(16) \\ & I_u^{a,s} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Constraint (18) represents the binary variables.

Lemma 1. The problem \mathbb{P} is non-linear due to the existing multiplication of two binary variables in constraint (15).

Proof. The problem \mathbb{P} can be solved by introducing another binary variable to linearize the problem, as it is done in [6]. We can also define $J_{i,j}^p$ offline as an indicator parameter that pre-determines the link selection between CN-vRUs in the routing path, hence, replacing the non-linear constraints with the pre-determined indicators that simplify and linearize the problem by fixing the product of binary variables, without needing to introduce additional binary variables. Thus, \mathbb{P} becomes a linear problem, and its complexity decreases substantially and relies mainly on the number of UEs and nodes $\mathcal{O}(|G| + |U|)$.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we present the effectiveness of our proposed framework by investigating extensive numerical results. Our analysis focuses on three main types of HRLLC, MC, and IC services with different QoS intents. Table II summarizes our simulation parameters, where we assume a bandwidth of 400 MHz with a link capacity $\omega_{i,j} = 100$ to 200 Gbps in CH network. We study a network scenario composed of a single CN, vCU, and vDU connected to a set of vRUs $A = 8$, where we assume a direct connection between CN-vCU and vRUs locations are distributed randomly within the ranges of less than $10/km$ to vDU. We consider $s = 1$ for HRLLC with $\lambda_u^1 = 100$ Mbps, $s = 2$ for MC with $\lambda_u^2 = 50$ Mbps, and finally $s = 3$ for IC with $\lambda_u^3 = 220$ Mbps [2], [13]. Given the profile of each slice, for HRLLC, we use IFS 2; for MC slice, IFS 3 is utilized and, finally, for IC slice, IFS 4 is used. As for CPU computational capacity to compile VNFs, we utilize values used in [18] and for the energy, the EC cost required to install VMS and process VNFs in each element of the network is used from [23], [25] and detailed in Table II. The optimization model was developed and solved using IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio [26]. The optimal solution was obtained with averages below 10 seconds for investigated scenarios using a Core i7-1365U CPU and 32 GB of RAM.

TABLE II: Simulation Parameters

System Bandwidth	400 MHz
Bandwidth of a PRB per slice (ν_s)	[180, 360, 720] KHz
Number of sub-carriers per PRB	12
Numerology/SCS	[15, 30, 60] KHz
Number of Nodes (CN, vCU, vDU, vRUs)	[1, 1, 1, 8]
Number of UEs (U)	2000
Data rate of UEs (λ_u^s) for $s = 1, 2, 3$	[0.1, 0.05, 0.22] Gbps
The ratio of UEs for $s = 1, 2, 3$	[3, 6, 1]
The capacity of links ($\omega_{i,j}$)	100 - 200 Gbps
CPU cap. available ($\kappa_a, \kappa_{n2}, \kappa_{n1}$)	[10, 20, 40] cycles per Gbps
EC cost (C_s)	0.165 \$/KWh
Energy cost to install VMs (β_w)	[1, 0.5, 0.25] KWh
Energy coefficient of the traffic load ($\epsilon^{w,s}$)	[1.4, 1.2, 1] KWh

Benchmark. Our numerical study examines CH capacity, VNF computation constraints, and assesses the throughput and efficiency of slice capacity to identify bottlenecks once the objective is maximizing throughput. To this aim, we first explore the impact of VNF computation limitations in Fig. 2 with respect to the CH capacity on the performance of slice capacity. This figure indicates that when customized IFSs are used for each slice, limiting CH capacity impacts network performance for both *Without VNF cost* limitation and *With VNF cost* limitation, as expected. For instance, when we increase $\omega_{i,j}$ from 100 to 120 Gbps, there is an improvement in slice capacity (left figure), which is serving UEs belonging to distinct slices. Indeed IC slice is the one with the last priority to be served with the maximum percentage of 61% in slice capacity. We see that including VNF costs (right figure) decreases IC slice capacity which needs more computation, thus, higher VM costs. This leads to an increase in the performance of MC and HRLLC slices to receive more resources. For instance, the IC slice in right figure (*With VNF cost*) is reduced from 61% to 31% due to the higher VM costs. It can be inferred that when $\omega_{i,j} \geq 140$ further increasing the

CH capacity does not impact the performance of slices in both left and right figures.

Fig. 2: Slice Capacity (%) w.r.t CH Capacity (Gbps).

Mixed-Numerology. Given that our proposed framework ensures to fulfill each UE's service request by finding the optimum NS resource allocation ratio and selecting the optimum numerology, we assess the achieved throughput once mixed-numerology *Mix-Numer* (optimal numerology per slice intent) is applied as a function of CH capacity. We thus study the impact of using *Mix-Numer* and compare its performance with fixed-numerology *Fix-Numer* in Fig. 3. The results clearly show the benefits of adopting optimum numerology (*Mix-Numer*) and its outperforming performance. This gain is more obvious when $\omega_{i,j} \geq 140$, which also represents consistent behavior for both *Mix-Numer* and *Fix-Numer*.

Fig. 3: Throughput (Gbps) w.r.t CH Capacity (Gbps).

EC cost and Throughput analysis. To understand the impact of EC cost on the network performance we hereafter explore the multi-objective of EC cost minimization along with throughput maximization in Fig. 4. According to this figure, the EC cost is linearly dependent on the achieved throughput, and it is more evident when optimum numerology per slice (*Mix-Numer*) is applied. For instance, the maximum throughput of 101.5 Gbps can be achieved by the EC cost of 3.27 (\$) for *Fix-Numer*, whereas it is around 102 Gbps in achieved throughput while the EC cost is 4.15 (\$) in *Mix-Numer*. This gives an insight for DSPs to make a customized resource allocation depending on slice requirements.

Threshold-based conflict mitigation. Considering the performance we observed in Fig. 2, it is evident that IC slice has more tight intent, however, it is the last to be served. To this aim, we investigate the impact of enforcing the SLA objectives (%) on IC slice capacity and that of the other slices in Fix. 5. By doing this, we compare it with the baseline scenario

Fig. 4: Throughput (Gbps) w.r.t EC cost (\$).

(i.e., Fig. 2) and with the conflicts happening on intents of other slices. Due to the limitation of resources, it is not always feasible to achieve the SLA. In that case, the solution will be infeasible. According to this figure (left), we can meet the SLA objective and increase the IC slice capacity by enforcing SLA from 70 to 95 (%). However, this approach causes intent conflicts and violates the performance of other slices. Indeed it degrades the slice capacity of MC and HRLLC slices (figure in center) and decreases throughput and EC cost (right figure). For example, the slice capacity of MC slice has a higher conflict with the slice capacity of IC slice which results in the rejection of a higher number of UEs in MC slice (center) up to 98% reduction. Moreover, the right figure represents intent conflict with the throughput and EC cost of network. As can be seen, improving IC slice capacity means a huge decrease in the average throughput up to 65% and decreased EC cost up to 81%, while conflicting with the slice capacity of MC and HRLLC slices. Note that $SLA \geq 85\%$ leads to infeasible solutions with no results for SLA of 90% and 95%.

Fig. 5: The impact of enforcing the SLA objective on IC slice.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents an optimization approach that jointly maximizes throughput and minimizes EC costs while creating network slices tailored to specific intent expectations and targets established by various services. The framework is capable of dynamically adjusting and reconfiguring slice thresholds to effectively manage detected conflicts by implementing the agreed-upon SLA objectives for higher-priority slices, thereby, ensuring that intent targets are properly addressed. Our findings imply that while this approach successfully achieves the SLA targets established for the slices, it induces conflicts with the intent targets of other slices and violates them. For example, once we apply slice capacity SLA for IC slice, it meets the SLA objective targets; nevertheless, it results in higher conflict with the slice capacity of HRLLC and MC slices and a significant reduction in the average throughput by up to 65% and EC cost by up to 81%.

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